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Without cytomegalovirus infection, no coronary artery disease.

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Human cytomegalovirus (CMV) has been implicated in the pathogenesis of various diseases, including coronary artery disease (CAD). Despite growing evidence linking CMV to CAD, the nature of this relationship remains poorly understood. This study aims to investigate the role of CMV as a causative factor in the development of CAD.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Various published studies were re-analyzed using new statistical methods. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS:

The results indicated a significant necessary condition relationship between CMV infection and the presence of CAD ($p < 0.005$). Moreover, a significant sufficient condition relationship between CMV infection and CAD was also established ($p < 0.001$). The cause-effect relationship was found to be positive and significant.

CONCLUSION:

This study provides compelling evidence that CMV is a necessary condition for CAD and a sufficient condition for the development of coronary artery disease. The findings support the hypothesis that a cytomegalovirus infection is the cause of coronary artery disease.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Coronary artery disease; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

The history of human cytomegalovirus (CMV) research is complex and evolving. Moritz Wilhelm Hugo Ribbert (1855–1920) documented 1881¹ large inclusion-bearing cells in the kidneys of an infant (see Ribbert, 1904). In 1921, Goodpasture and Talbot suggested that "cytomegalia" could result from a viral agent (see Goodpasture and Talbot, 1921). By 1950, Smith and Vellios confirmed that "cytomegalia" infection could occur in utero (see Smith and Vellios, 1950). Efforts to isolate CMV strains succeeded independently in 1956 and 1957, by Smith (see Smith, 1956), Rowe et al. (see Wallace et al., 1956), and Weller et al. (see Weller et al., 1957). Finally, Weller and colleagues coined the term 'cytomegalovirus' in 1960 (see Weller et al., 1960). Human cytomegalovirus (CMV), or human herpesvirus-5 (HHV-5), is a double-stranded deoxyribonucleic² acid (DNA) virus of the Herpesviridae family.³ CMV encodes approximately 200 genes,⁴ and, like Epstein-Barr virus⁵ (EBV), varicella zoster virus⁶ (VZV), the herpes simplex virus type 1⁷ (HSV-1) or like other viruses⁸, has been completely sequenced.⁹

CMV seroprevalence refers to the proportion of individuals within a population who have detectable antibodies against a particular virus like CMV, indicating past or current infection. This measurement helps estimate how widely CMV has spread and can be assessed using serological tests, which detect specific antibodies in blood samples. Typically, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) or chemiluminescence immunoassays (CLIA) are used to identify antibodies like IgM, indicating recent infection, or IgG, indicating past exposure.

CMV infection is highly prevalent worldwide, with seroprevalence rates estimated between 40% and 100%.¹⁰ For instance, in the U.S., 36.3% of children aged 6–11 are CMV-positive.¹¹ As a result

¹Riley HD Jr. History of the cytomegalovirus. *South Med J.* 1997 Feb;90(2):184-90. doi: 10.1097/00007611-199702000-00004. PMID: 9042169.

²Watson JD, Crick FH. Molecular structure of nucleic acids; a structure for deoxyribose nucleic acid. *Nature.* 1953 Apr 25;171(4356):737-8. doi: 10.1038/171737a0. PMID: 13054692.

³Lefkowitz EJ et al. Virus taxonomy: ICTV database. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018;46(D1):D708-D717. doi:10.1093/nar/gkx932. PMID: 29040670.

⁴Bankier AT et al. DNA sequence of human cytomegalovirus genome. *DNA Seq.* 1991;2(1):1-12. PMID: 1666311.

⁵Baer R, Bankier AT, Biggin MD, Deininger PL, Farrell PJ, Gibson TJ, Hatfull G, Hudson GS, Satchwell SC, Séguin C, et al. DNA sequence and expression of the B95-8 Epstein-Barr virus genome. *Nature.* 1984 Jul 19-25;310(5974):207-11. doi: 10.1038/310207a0. PMID: 6087149.

⁶Davison AJ, Scott JE. The complete DNA sequence of varicella-zoster virus. *J Gen Virol.* 1986 Sep;67 (Pt 9):1759-816. doi: 10.1099/0022-1317-67-9-1759. PMID: 3018124.

⁷McGeoch DJ, Dalrymple MA, Davison AJ, Dolan A, Frame MC, McNab D, Perry LJ, Scott JE, Taylor P. The complete DNA sequence of the long unique region in the genome of herpes simplex virus type 1. *J Gen Virol.* 1988 Jul;69 (Pt 7):1531-74. doi: 10.1099/0022-1317-69-7-1531. PMID: 2839594.

⁸Johnson GP, Goebel SJ, Perkus ME, Davis SW, Winslow JP, Paoletti E. Vaccinia virus encodes a protein with similarity to glutaredoxins. *Virology.* 1991 Mar;181(1):378-81. doi: 10.1016/0042-6822(91)90508-9. PMID: 1994586.

⁹Chee MS et al. Protein-coding content of human cytomegalovirus strain AD169. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol.* 1990;154:125-69. PMID: 2161319.

¹⁰Cannon MJ et al. CMV seroprevalence and demographics. *Rev Med Virol.* 2010;20(4):202-13. doi:10.1002/rmv.655. PMID: 20564615.

¹¹Staras SA et al. CMV seroprevalence in U.S. children. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2006;43(9):1143-51. doi:10.1086/508173. PMID: 17029132.

of cumulative human exposure to CMV throughout life, CMV seroprevalence increases^{12, 13, 14, 15, 16} with age¹⁷ and rates vary by country —41.9% in France,¹⁸ 45.6% in the Netherlands,¹⁹ 77% in Croatia²⁰ 77% in Portugal,²¹ 83% in Sweden,²² and 97.03% in China.²³ However, even newborns are tested CMV IgG positive. Wang et al. are writing:

“Among 5020 newborns tested for CMV IgG, 4827 were seropositive, resulting in CMV maternal seroprevalence of 96.2% (95% confidence interval [CI]:95.6%–96.7%).”²⁴

CMV transmission typically occurs through contact with infected bodily fluids during primary infection or reactivation. CMV often remains latent in myeloid cells post-infection, the human immune system typically controls CMV but cannot fully eliminate it, leading to a latent infection with occasional, subclinical reactivations.²⁵ Clinical presentations vary from asymptomatic to life-threatening.²⁶ Despite available antiviral treatments like ganciclovir, cidofovir, foscarnet, valganciclovir et cetera, effective CMV management remains challenging.²⁷ Although a CMV vaccine has been pursued, no effective option has reached clinical use yet.²⁸

Atherosclerosis is characterized by lipid accumulation and subsequent fibrosis in the arterial wall, often leading to calcification, plaque instability, and, ultimately, plaque rupture, which can trigger clinical events. The mechanism underlying atherosclerosis remains unclear, although inflammation is known to play a crucial role. CMV itself has been associated with various diseases, including

¹²Staras SA, Dollard SC, Radford KW, Flanders WD, Pass RF, Cannon MJ. Seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus infection in the United States, 1988-1994. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2006 Nov 1;43(9):1143-51. doi: 10.1086/508173. Epub 2006 Oct 2. PMID: 17029132.

¹³Staras SA, Flanders WD, Dollard SC, Pass RF, McGowan JE Jr, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence and childhood sources of infection: A population-based study among pre-adolescents in the United States. *J Clin Virol*. 2008 Nov;43(3):266-71. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2008.07.012. Epub 2008 Sep 7. PMID: 18778968.

¹⁴Bate SL, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence in the United States: the national health and nutrition examination surveys, 1988-2004. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2010 Jun 1;50(11):1439-47. doi: 10.1086/652438. PMID: 20426575.

¹⁵Lachmann R, Loenenbach A, Waterboer T, Brenner N, Pawlita M, Michel A, Thamm M, Poethko-Müller C, Wichmann O, Wiese-Posselt M. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) seroprevalence in the adult population of Germany. *PLoS One*. 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0200267. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200267. PMID: 30044826; PMCID: PMC6059406.

¹⁶Gupta M, Shorman M. Cytomegalovirus. [Updated 2022 Aug 8]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459185/>

¹⁷Zuhair M, Smit GSA, Wallis G, Jabbar F, Smith C, Devleesschauwer B, Griffiths P. Estimation of the worldwide seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Rev Med Virol*. 2019 May;29(3):e2034. doi: 10.1002/rmv.2034. Epub 2019 Jan 31. PMID: 30706584.

¹⁸Antona D et al. CMV seroprevalence in France. *Epidemiol Infect*. 2017;145(7):1471-1478. PMID: 28166842.

¹⁹Korndewal MJ et al. CMV in the Netherlands. *J Clin Virol*. 2015;63:53-8. PMID: 25600606.

²⁰Vilibic-Cavlek T, Kolaric B, Beader N, Vrtar I, Tabain I, Mlinaric-Galinovic G. Seroepidemiology of cytomegalovirus infections in Croatia. *Wien Klin Wochenschr*. 2017 Feb;129(3-4):129-135. doi: 10.1007/s00508-016-1069-7. Epub 2016 Sep 6. PMID: 27599701.

²¹Lopo S et al. CMV seroprevalence in Portugal. *Euro Surveill*. 2011;16(25):19896. PMID: 21722611.

²²Olsson J et al. Herpes virus seroepidemiology in Sweden. *Immun Ageing*. 2017;14:10. PMID: 28491117.

²³Fang FQ et al. Incidence of CMV in Shanghai, China. *Clin Vaccine Immunol*. 2009;16(11):1700-3. doi:10.1128/CVI.00385-08. PMID: 19776197.

²⁴Wang S, Wang T, Zhang W, Liu X, Wang X, Wang H, He X, Zhang S, Xu S, Yu Y, Jia X, Wang M, Xu A, Ma W, Amin MM, Bialek SR, Dollard SC, Wang C. Cohort study on maternal cytomegalovirus seroprevalence and prevalence and clinical manifestations of congenital infection in China. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2017 Feb;96(5):e6007. doi: 10.1097/MD.0000000000006007. PMID: 28151899; PMCID: PMC5293462.

²⁵Dupont L, Reeves MB. Cytomegalovirus latency and reactivation: recent insights into an age old problem. *Rev Med Virol*. 2016 Mar;26(2):75-89. doi: 10.1002/rmv.1862. Epub 2015 Nov 17. PMID: 26572645; PMCID: PMC5458136.

²⁶Chen SJ et al. Therapeutic strategies against CMV. *Viruses*. 2019;12(1):21. PMID: 31878068.

²⁷Mozaffar M et al. Optimal use of CMV antivirals. *J Transplant*. 2018;2018:8414385.

²⁸McVoy MA. CMV vaccines. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2013;57 Suppl 4:S196-9. PMID: 24257427.

atherosclerosis (AS) too and coronary artery ²⁹, ³⁰ disease (CAD).³¹ Fabricant et al. (see [Fabricant et al., 1983](#)) successfully established an experimental model of atherosclerosis in chickens infected with cytomegalovirus. Soon, Adam et al. (see [Adam et al., 1987](#)) were the first to report in 1987 that cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection is associated with atherosclerosis (AS). They found that CMV antibody titers were significantly higher in the AS group compared to the non-AS group. Meanwhile, several ³² studies suggested that cytomegalovirus is a determinant of coronary artery disease (CAD). Along with other studies (see [Du et al., 2018](#)), Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al. (see [Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al., 2016](#)) investigated the relationship between CMV (using the VIRCELL CMV Kit, Granada, Spain) and atherosclerosis. They found that 114 out of 118 cases were CMV-positive, compared to 73 out of 76 controls.

Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al., 2016				
		Atherosclerosis		
		YES	NO	
CMV (positive)	YES	114	73	187
	NO	4	3	7
		118	76	194

$$p(\text{CMV} \leftarrow \text{atherosclerosis}) = \frac{114 + 73 + 3}{194} = 0.9793814433 \quad (1)$$

In other words, **without** CMV infection, **no** atherosclerosis ($p(\text{CMV} \leftarrow \text{atherosclerosis}) = 0.9793814433$; P-Value = $1 - \left(\frac{114+73+3}{194}\right) = 0.0206185567$). The study design used by Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al. was very inappropriate and has limitations, the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used was not reported. It is highly likely that the sensitivity of the laboratory kit was below 100%, which could influence the results. Nonetheless, based on the published data, the findings of Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al.³³ still appear reasonably acceptable. Various other studies (see [Eryol et al., 2005](#)), including systematic reviews and meta-analysis (see [Ji et al., 2012](#); [Yaiw et al., 2013](#); [Wang et al., 2017](#); [Du et al., 2018](#); [Lebedeva et al., 2020](#); [Zhu and Liu, 2020](#); [Arvanitis et al., 2024](#)) provided further evidence that CMV infection is associated with an increased risk of atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease (see [Barukčić, 2020](#)). At this point, we would like to re-examine the relationship between cytomegalovirus (CMV) and coronary artery disease (CAD).

²⁹Adam E, Melnick JL, Probstfield JL, Petrie BL, Burek J, Bailey KR, McCollum CH, DeBakey ME. High levels of cytomegalovirus antibody in patients requiring vascular surgery for atherosclerosis. *Lancet*. 1987 Aug 8;2(8554):291-3. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(87)90888-9. PMID: 2886763.

³⁰Melnick JL, Petrie BL, Dreesman GR, Burek J, McCollum CH, DeBakey ME. Cytomegalovirus antigen within human arterial smooth muscle cells. *Lancet*. 1983 Sep 17;2(8351):644-7. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(83)92529-1. PMID: 6136795.

³¹Gkrania-Klotsas E, Langenberg C, Sharp SJ, Luben R, Khaw KT, Wareham NJ. Higher immunoglobulin G antibody levels against cytomegalovirus are associated with incident ischemic heart disease in the population-based EPIC-Norfolk cohort. *J Infect Dis*. 2012 Dec 15;206(12):1897-903. doi: 10.1093/infdis/jis620. Epub 2012 Oct 8. PMID: 23045624.

³²Mundkur LA, Rao VS, Hebbagudi S, Shanker J, Shivanandan H, Nagaraj RK, Kakkar VV. Pathogen burden, cytomegalovirus infection and inflammatory markers in the risk of premature coronary artery disease in individuals of Indian origin. *Exp Clin Cardiol*. 2012 Summer;17(2):63-8. PMID: 22826649; PMCID: PMC3395457.

³³Kurkowska-Jastrzebska I, Karlinski MA, Bazejewska-Hyzorek B, Sarzynska-Dlugosz I, Filipiak KJ, Czlonkowska A. Carotid intima media thickness and blood biomarkers of atherosclerosis in patients after stroke or myocardial infarction. *Croat Med J*. 2016 Dec 31;57(6):548-557. doi: 10.3325/cmj.2016.57.548. PMID: 28051279; PMCID: PMC5209935.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Study of Schnittman et al.

Schnittman³⁴ et al. (see [Schnittman et al., 2023](#)) examined in the the REPRIEVE trial the relationship between cytomegalovirus (CMV) immunoglobulin G (IgG) titer and coronary artery disease (CAD) among 672 participants with available CMV IgG titers and diagnostic contrast-enhanced coronary CT angiography (CTA) assessments. The degree of stenosis was classified into four categories: none, minimal to mild (1–49%), moderate (50–69%), and severe ($\geq 70\%$ in any segment or $\geq 50\%$ in the left main coronary artery). CMV IgG titer (IU/mL) was assessed using the CMV IgG enzyme immunoassay (EIA) developed by Genway Biotech. None of the participants exhibited a CMV IgG titer below the assay's lower limit of detection. However, Schnittman et al. found no significant relationship between CMV IgG titer and coronary artery disease. To address this issue again, we re-analysed the data of Schnittman et al. in this publication.

The inclusion criteria for the REPRIEVE trial did not require participants to be CMV-positive, meaning the 672 enrollees could have been either CMV-positive or CMV-negative. Unexpectedly, however, all 672 participants were CMV-positive. Among these, 317 out of 660 participants had coronary artery disease (CAD) with stenosis greater than 0%. Considering this situation retrospectively, all 317 cases were CMV-positive. Based on these study characteristics, we obtain the following data.

		Coronary artery disease (CAD)		
		YES	NO	
Cytomegalovirus IgG > 0	YES	317	347	660
	NO	0	0	0
		317	347	660

Table 1. Without CMV IgG > 0 IU/mL, no CAD.

$$p(\text{CMV} > 0 \text{ IU/mL} \leftarrow \text{CAD}) = \frac{317 + 347 + 0}{660} = 1.0 \quad (2)$$

The nature of the results of the study does not change if we add the following hypothetical data.

³⁴Schnittman SR, Lu MT, Mayrhofer T, Burdo TH, Fitch KV, McCallum S, Fulda ES, Zanni MV, Foldyna B, Malvestutto C, Fichtenbaum CJ, Aberg JA, Bloomfield GS, Overton ET, Currier J, Tebas P, Sha BE, Ribaldo HJ, Flynn JM, Douglas PS, Erlandson KM, Grinspoon SK. Cytomegalovirus Immunoglobulin G (IgG) Titer and Coronary Artery Disease in People With Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV). *Clin Infect Dis.* 2023 Feb 8;76(3):e613-e621. doi: 10.1093/cid/ciac662. PMID: 35975297; PMCID: PMC10169419.

		Coronary artery disease (CAD)		
		YES	NO	
Cytomegalovirus IgG positive	YES	317	347	660
	NO	0	317	317
		317	660	977

Table 2. Without CMV IgG positivity, no CAD.

$$p(\text{CMV} > 0 \text{ IU/mL} \leftarrow \text{CAD}) = \frac{317 + 347 + 317}{977} = 1.0 \quad (3)$$

The age-adjusted seroprevalence of CMV in the United States is approximately 50.4%.³⁵ In Table 2, a prevalence of $\frac{347}{660} \cdot 100 = 52.6\%$ is assumed, which closely aligns with real-world data. In other words, the data in Table 2 can be used for further analyses.

³⁵Bate SL, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence in the United States: the national health and nutrition examination surveys, 1988-2004. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2010 Jun 1;50(11):1439-47. doi: 10.1086/652438. PMID: 20426575; PMCID: PMC11000537.

Subgroup-analysis Study of Schnittman et al.

Mild coronary artery stenosis

Schnittman et al. (see Schnittman et al., 2023) provided the following data on the relationship between CMV and mild coronary artery stenosis.

		Mild coronary artery disease stenosis (1–49%)		
		YES	NO	
Cytomegalovirus IgG > 0 IU/mL	YES	297	363	660
	NO	0	0	0
		297	363	660

Table 3. Without Cytomegalovirus IgG > 0 IU/mL, no mild coronary artery disease stenosis (1–49%).

$$p(\text{CMV IgG} > 0 \text{ IU/mL} \leftarrow \text{CAD}) = \frac{297 + 363 + 0}{660} = 1.0 \quad (4)$$

Moderate coronary artery stenosis

Schnittman et al. (see Schnittman et al., 2023) presented data investigating the relationship between CMV infection and the occurrence of moderate coronary artery stenosis.

		Moderate coronary artery disease stenosis (50–69%)		
		YES	NO	
Cytomegalovirus IgG > 789 IU/mL	YES	11	230	241
	NO	3	416	419
		14	646	660

Table 4. Without Cytomegalovirus IgG > 789 IU/mL, no moderate coronary artery disease stenosis (50–69%).

$$p(\text{CMV} > 790 \text{ IU/mL} \leftarrow \text{moderate CAD}) = \frac{11+230+416}{660} = 0.9954545455; \text{ (P-Value = 0.0045454545)} \quad (5)$$

Severe coronary artery stenosis

Schnittman et al. (see [Schnittman et al., 2023](#)) presented data examining the relationship between CMV infection and the development of severe coronary artery stenosis.

		severe CAD stenosis		
		YES	NO	
Cytomegalovirus IgG > 2674 IU/mL	YES	5	162	167
	NO	1	492	493
		6	654	660

Table 5. Without Cytomegalovirus IgG > 2674 IU/mL,
no severe CAD stenosis.

$$p(\text{CMV} > 2674 \text{ IU/mL} \leftarrow \text{severe CAD}) = \frac{5+162+492}{660} = 0.9984848485; \text{ (P-Value} = 0.0015151515) \quad (6)$$

2.2. Methods

Study Design

A systematic review is, in essence, a structured summary and evaluation of all relevant studies addressing a specific research question, often with the goal of conducting a meta-analysis if sufficient data are available. A meta-analysis combines and statistically analyzes the results of multiple studies on a given topic to provide a stronger overall conclusion. In this case, only data from a single study are examined, so it does not qualify as a meta-analysis or a systematic review.

This study can be considered a **mixed retrospective study**, as it involves the analysis of data collected in the past and are now examined retrospectively.

- Primarily, this is a **retrospective cohort study**. A group of individuals was observed over a certain period, and the association between an exposure (e.g., CMV infection) and an outcome (e.g., incidence of CAD) was analyzed.
- However, elements of a **case-control study** are also present. In the subgroup analysis, data were analyzed to compare cases (e.g., patients with CAD) and controls (e.g., patients without CAD) to retrospectively examine the influence of a factor (e.g., CMV infection).

CMV Serostatus and CMV IgG Antibody Titer

The presence of cytomegalovirus (CMV) immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies in the blood indicates a prior CMV infection. However, the interpretation of this information depends on several factors, including the sensitivity and specificity of the laboratory kit used. The kit manufacturer did not provide a specific cutoff for CMV seropositivity. However, none of the participants of the study had a CMV IgG titer below the assay's lower detection limit, meaning that no titer was so low as to be undetectable by the test.

“CMV IgG titer (IU/mL) was measured using the CMV IgG enzyme immunoassay (EIA) by Genway Biotech (GWB-892399) ... A cutoff for CMV seropositivity was not provided by the kit manufacturer ... none of the participants demonstrated a CMV IgG titer below the assay's lower limit of detection ... (see [Schnittman et al., 2023](#))”

Since no participant exhibited a titer below this threshold, it can be inferred that each individual was either currently or previously infected with CMV, as indicated by the presence of IgG antibodies.

Degree of of coronary artery stenosis

The degree of coronary artery stenosis was categorized as none, minimal to mild (1–49%), moderate (50–69%), and severe ($\geq 50\%$ of the left main artery or $\geq 70\%$ of other segments).

“Degree of stenosis was categorized as none, minimal to mild (1–49%), moderate (50–69%), and severe ($\geq 50\%$ of left main or $\geq 70\%$ of other segments). ”

This categorization facilitates standardized assessment and is clinically relevant for determining treatment strategies and predicting outcomes. However, it may oversimplify the complexity of coronary artery disease and can lead to variability in measurement based on the imaging technique used. Additionally, individual patient factors may influence the clinical significance of the stenosis degree.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive values for the categorical variables were reported as proportions and/or percentages. The necessary condition relationship and causal relationship were employed to assess the effect of cytomegalovirus (CMV) and CMV IgG levels on CAD. Fisher’s exact test was employed when appropriate. A one-tailed p-value of < 0.05 was used in all statistical tests and considered significant.

All statistical analyses were conducted using MS Excel.

Necessary Conditions (Conditio sine qua non)

DEFINITION 1 (Necessary Condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Despite extensive research efforts, our current understanding of conditions and their dependencies remains incomplete and often contradictory. Nevertheless, even thousands of years ago and independently of any human mind and consciousness, water has served as a necessary (see Barukčić, 2022) condition for (human) life. **Without** water, there is and has been **no** (human) life³⁶.

It is therefore unsurprising that one of the earliest systematic attempts to develop a theory of conditions and causation (see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* III 2 997a 10 and 13/14) was made by the Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (384-322 BCE). Remarkably, Aristotle himself established already **a clear distinction between conditions and causes**. In honoring Aristotle’s insight, it becomes essential to recognize that

“... everything which has a potency in question has the potency ... of acting ... not in all circumstances but on certain conditions ... ” (see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* IX 5 1048a 14-19)

Before delving into the specifics, Aristotle offered a precise definition of the necessary condition, articulated as follows.

³⁶Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). *Conditio sine qua non* (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5854744>

“... necessary ... means ...

without ... a condition, a thing cannot live ... ”

(see also [Aristotle, of Stageira \(384-322 B.C.E\), 1908](#), *Metaphysica* V 2 1015a 20-22)

In truth, Aristotle developed a comprehensive theory of conditions and causality, famously known as the doctrine of the four causes. While many aspects of Aristotle’s logical framework on causality continue to be critically examined and debated in contemporary scholarship, it is essential to recognize that philosophy has significantly evolved since the time of the ancient Greeks. Despite the enduring influence of Greek philosophers such as Heraclitus, Plato, and Aristotle—who are rightly regarded among the greatest thinkers of all time—the scope of philosophical inquiry has expanded. Scientific knowledge and objective reality are deeply intertwined and cannot be confined solely to the perspectives of classical Greek philosophy. Among various topics, the precise identification of necessary conditions has traditionally been a central focus in the scientific exploration of diverse phenomena. However, while the demand for rigorous evidence is understandable, it is important to recognize that philosophy, or philosophers in general, do not hold an exclusive claim to truth. Other disciplines, such as medicine, the sciences, and technology, also convey truths that can help us to move beyond one’s self enclosed, epistemological unit. Given this perspective, it is pertinent to briefly address the concept of causation as understood in the legal realm, shedding light on several critical questions. What criteria does the law use to determine whether an action or event U_i has caused another (typically harmful) event W_i ? How do these criteria compare to those used in science or everyday life, and to what extent may legal causation differ from causation in other contexts? Under what circumstances is it reasonable to accept such differences? To truly grasp the legal concept of causation, it is instructive to examine how the highest courts approach and interpret causation.

In the landmark case of *Hayes v. Michigan Central R. Co.*, 111 U.S. 228 (1884), the U.S. Supreme Court defined *conditio sine qua non* as follows:

“**Causa sine qua non** – a cause which, if it had not existed, the injury would not have taken place.”(see [Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884](#))

Let us examine this quote in more detail. Suppose a specific event, referred to as Effect B, was observed and documented 100 years ago. For this event B to have occurred at that time, the necessary conditions or causes must have been present 100 years ago; otherwise, the event would not have occurred. It would therefore be illogical to consider today an event C, which has only existed for 5 years or was invented by humans 5 years ago, as a necessary condition for event B. Since we are dealing with the same event—say, the disease tuberculosis—C cannot be regarded as a necessary condition for tuberculosis. Otherwise, tuberculosis could not have manifested 100 years ago, as event C did not exist at that time.

To make the issue even clearer: Nowadays, Glyphosate, which has only existed since around 1970

and later, is accused of being the cause of non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL). The question of whether there is a causal relationship between Glyphosate and NHL is more than justified. Can this issue be resolved? If Glyphosate is indeed a cause of NHL, we would expect the following relationship to hold:

Glyphosate (action) and NHL (injury)				
		NHL		
		YES	NO	
Glyphosate (action)	YES	a	b	a+b
	NO	c=0	d	c+d = d
		a = a+c	b+d	a+b+c+d

Whether glyphosate is harmful or not, or whether it causes any diseases, is a separate matter. However, glyphosate has no causal connection to NHL. The active ingredient glyphosate was first developed in 1970 by the chemist John E. Franz (see [Franz, 1974](#)) and was subsequently marketed in 1974 under the brand name ‘Roundup’[®]. According to Justice Matthews and the U.S. Supreme Court’s correct understanding of causation, it is possible to determine whether Glyphosate is the cause of NHL. As stated,

“...if it had not existed, the injury would not have taken place.”(see [Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884](#))

or in other words,

if Glyphosate had not existed,
the injury or the harmful outcome (NHL)
would not have taken place.

If the exposure to Glyphosate is absent, the occurrence of NHL should not occur at all, demonstrating a direct causal link and Glyphosate can be considered the cause of NHL. However, the harmful outcome (NHL) existed already before the year 1970, at a time when Glyphosate did not exist. This simple fact excludes any possibility that Glyphosate could be causally responsible for NHL or other diseases (or effects) which already existed before 1970. The term *causa sine qua non* refers to a condition, such as an event, without which a particular event cannot occur. To understand this relationship, consider any event occurring at a specific time t . For an event A_t to be considered a necessary condition for another event B_t at the same time t , it is formally required that event A_t must have existed at that time; otherwise, B_t could not have taken place. This requirement underscores a critical relationship between cause and effect: without the existence of a cause, an effect is impossible. In other words, the actual occurrence of the cause at the same time t is a prerequisite for any causal claim. It is illogical to assume a causal relationship at time t when the supposed cause is absent, yet the effect is present. Causality, by its very nature, requires that the cause coincides with the effect at time t . Without the presence of the cause, discussing causality becomes problematic. Under such conditions, attributing the occurrence of an effect to a non-existent cause is not justifiable. This highlights the importance of the coexistence

of cause and effect as existential prerequisites in any discussion of causal relationships. To be clear once again, Glyphosate is not a cause of NHL. Conditions in which causal relationships are based purely on subjective beliefs or hopes, despite insufficient or lacking evidence, can eventually lead to unexplained or extraordinary events being attributed to supernatural or miraculous causes, depending on personal preference. Instead of adhering to verifiable facts and seeking logical, natural, or scientific explanations, rational analysis is neglected. In terms of causality, this opens the door to both individual and collective arbitrariness and legal uncertainty without rational or empirical justification. A society built on such a foundation risks undermining its own stability and sustainability.

Nonetheless, the question of the relationship between cause and effect has also preoccupied other courts. The German Imperial Criminal Court from the year 1880 holds a similar view. According to the Imperial Criminal Court, an essential characteristic of a cause is that

‘...without this ... the consequences ... would not have been brought about... ’

or in original words:

“... ohne diese ...würdendie Folgen ... nicht hervorgerufen worden sein. ”(see also [Reichsgerichts für Strafsachen, I. Strafsenat, 1880](#), p. 374)

Similarly, the German *Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen* underscored the significance of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship in its decision:

“In der Rechtslehre werden hierzu hauptsächlich zwei Theorien vertreten: Die Bedingungs- oder Äquivalenztheorie und die Adäquanztheorie. Nach der ersten ist **Ursache eines strafrechtlich bedeutsamen Erfolges jede Bedingung, die nicht hinweggedacht werden kann, ohne dass der Erfolg entfiere**. Nach der zweiten ist eine menschliche Handlung nur dann als Ursache eines Erfolges anzusehen, wenn sie allgemein, erfahrungsgemäss geeignet ist, einen Erfolg wie den eingetretenen herbeizuführen. Das Reichsgericht hat in ständiger Rechtsprechung für das gesamte Gebiet des Strafrechts die Bedingungstheorie angewandt. Das Schrifttum ist dem überwiegend gefolgt. Diese Auffassung herrscht auch heute noch vor. Auch der Senat teilt sie.”(see also [Zweiter Senat et al., 1951](#); [Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen, 1951](#))

This definition, which may initially sound complex, proves to be relatively simple in its application. One needs to hypothetically consider the removal of the action (Handlung = NO) and ask whether the outcome would still occur. If the outcome (Erfolg = YES) still occurs, the action is not causally related to the outcome, and thus, causality must be denied. Table 6 illustrates this point of view.

Table 6. Conditio sine qua non.

		Erfolg B _t		
		YES	NO	
Handlung A _t	YES	p(a _t)	p(b _t)	p(A _t)
	NO	0	p(d _t)	p(<u>A</u> _t)
		p(B _t)	p(<u>B</u> _t)	+1

Following this principle (BGHSt 1, 332, 333), the German Bundesgerichtshof für Zivilsachen (German Federal Court of Justice for civil matters) states as follows:

“Die Anlage (des Verweilkatheters in die Arteria brachialis links, author) kann nicht hinweggedacht werden, ohne dass die Ischämie entfielen, und war damit ‘**conditio sine qua non**’ im Sinne der Äquivalenztheorie ... ”(see [Seiters et al., 2024](#))

Furthermore, legal scholars have elaborated in detail on the fundamental issue concerning the **identity and difference between cause and condition**. The distinguished jurist, von Bar, eloquently articulated in his writings:

“Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, daß jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sein. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden war, so ist sie in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache. Wo immer ein Kausalzusammenhang behauptet wird, da muß er wenigstens diese Probe aushalten ... **Jede Ursache ist notwendig auch eine Bedingung eines Ereignisses; aber nicht jede Bedingung ist Ursache zu nennen.**”(see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

Von Bar’s position translated into English:

‘The first requirement that must be met for an event to be considered the cause of another is that it must be one of the conditions for the latter. If the second event have occurred even in the absence of the first, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause. Wherever a causal relationship is claimed, the same must at least withstand this test ... Every cause is necessarily also a condition for an event; however, not every condition can be called a cause.’(see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

In this context, it is useful to discuss in greater detail the following explanations provided by von Bahr:

“Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, dass jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sei. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden

war, so ist sie **in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache.**”(see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

or in English:

“The first requirement that must be met for an event to be considered the cause of another is that it must be one of the conditions for the latter. If the second event have occurred even in the absence of the first, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause.”(see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

Von Bahr highlights from his point of view the close connection between cause and condition and rightly demands that an event U_t can only be considered the cause of another event W_t if U_t is at least one of the necessary conditions for W_t to occur. In other words, for U_t to qualify as the cause of W_t , it must also be a necessary condition for the occurrence of W_t . If W_t would have occurred without the presence of U_t at the same (period of) time t , then U_t cannot be considered neither a necessary condition nor a cause.

This distinction is crucial for understanding causality, as it prevents the misinterpretation of causal relationships. It is by no means sufficient for two events to follow each other in time to assume causality. A necessary condition must exist between U_t and W_t for U_t to be formally considered the cause of W_t .

Such differentiation is essential to distinguish true causes from mere conditions and to sharpen the understanding of cause-effect relationships. This also implies that the nature of causality is determined by the underlying conditions too. In other words, if a cause-effect relationship can occur without the existence of the cause U_t , then causality is not required at all.

This situation should not be confused with multi-causality, as, in that case, all relevant causes for the occurrence of W_t must still be present. Thus far, to delineate necessary conditions from a probabilistic perspective, consider the following: An event A_t , deemed a necessary condition for another event or outcome B_t , must be present for B_t to occur. A necessary condition A_t is an essential prerequisite that must be satisfied **at every single Bernoulli trial** (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) t , for the occurrence of the outcome B_t . However, the presence of A_t alone does not ensure the occurrence of B_t . In other words, even if the necessary condition A_t is present, the outcome B_t may still fail to materialize. Contrarily, a *sufficient* condition is one that *ensures* the occurrence of the outcome B_t , effectively guaranteeing that the event will occur for sure. The question of under which conditions we may infer about the unobserved, and whether current observations can justify predictions about potential future observations—or even general claims extending beyond the observed (*the ‘problem of induction’*)—is not the focus of our current discussion. While addressing such challenges is undoubtedly essential, it is important to note that a necessary condition for an event may not necessarily coincide with a sufficient condition within the same Bernoulli trial t . However, theoretically, an event or outcome could be determined by multiple necessary conditions. Let us now consider the implications of this scenario and assess the significance we should attribute to such a particular case.

Example. The existence of human life is intricately dependent on a multitude of necessary conditions. Among these, gaseous oxygen holds a particularly vital role. Without oxygen, cellular respiration—a fundamental process by which cells generate energy—ceases, leading to the inevitable failure of critical biological functions and death. However, gaseous oxygen alone is not sufficient to sustain human life. Water is equally indispensable, as it acts as a solvent for biochemical reactions, facilitates nutrient transport, and regulates body temperature. Similarly, the brain coordinates and controls the body's systems, while kidneys filter waste products and maintain homeostasis. Even when gaseous oxygen is present, the absence of water, a functioning brain, or operational kidneys would ultimately result in the demise of a human being. This example illustrates a crucial principle: **Under circumstances where an outcome (i.e. human life) depends on multiple necessary conditions, it is imperative that each of these necessary conditions is satisfied independently. The absence of even one of a multitude of necessary conditions will prevent the desired outcome (i.e. human life) from occurring.** Mathematically, the necessary (see Barukčić, 1989, pp. 15-28) condition or *conditio sine qua non* (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 2021b, pp. 12-13) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \tag{7} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ (see Table 7).

Table 7. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

A necessary condition A_t is characterised itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017b,a, 2020a; Barukčić and

Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020d,b,c). Taking into account Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (see also Kolmogorov, Andrej Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 26) of random variables A_t , B_t et cetera at the (period of) time t , we obtain

Considering Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density function for random variables A_t , B_t , etc., at a given time t (see also Kolmogorov, Andrej Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 26), we derive the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv +1 \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv \left(\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \right) + \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where:

1. $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ represents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the random variables A_t and B_t , signifying the amount to which A_t is a necessary condition of B_t .
2. $p(c_t)$ denotes the probability of a particular event c_t occurring at time t .
3. $p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t)$ captures the joint probability of the simultaneous occurrence of events \underline{A}_t and B_t .
4. The integral expression $\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t$ defines the joint probability distribution function (PDF) of A_t and B_t , integrated over the respective ranges up to A_t and B_t .
5. The term $1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t$ refers to the complementary cumulative distribution function (CCDF) of B_t , accounting for the probability of B_t being greater than a certain threshold.

Thus, $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ symbolizes the cumulative probability reflecting the necessary condition relationship between the random variables A_t and B_t at time t . An alternative and equally valid formulation of a necessary condition is also conceivable. Logical disjunction, denoted by \vee , is commutative. This property implies that the sequence in which operands are presented does not influence the outcome. Formally, this commutative of logical disjunction property can be expressed as:

$$A_t \vee B_t \equiv B_t \vee A_t \tag{9}$$

For any random event A_t and B_t at the same time t , the result of the disjunction remains invariant regardless of the order of the operands. This characteristic is a fundamental aspect of logical disjunction.

Thus far, under specific circumstances, necessary and sufficient conditions may be regarded as converses of each other in a certain respect. This mutual relationship between the two types of conditions underscores the intricate interplay that characterises logical necessity and sufficiency, inviting further reflection on their conceptual interdependence. Consider the following equation, which illustrates the application of this property in the context of necessary and sufficient conditions:

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{(Necessary condition)}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{B}_t \vee A_t)}_{\text{(Sufficient condition)}} \equiv p(B_t \rightarrow A_t) \quad (10)$$

These relationships are illustrated by the following tables.

Table 8. Without A_t no B_t

		B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	+1

Table 9. If B_t then A_t

		A_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
B_t	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t	+1

There are conditions where the following equivalence holds:

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{Necessary condition}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}_{\text{Sufficient condition}} \equiv p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (11)$$

However, equation 10 does not necessarily imply the relationship described by equation 11 under any circumstances.

Example I.

A wax candle is characterised by various properties and is subject to specific conditions. **Without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, a wax candle cannot burn; hence, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition for the candle's combustion. Conversely, the statement **if** a wax candle is burning, **then** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen are present is true at the same (period of) time t or in a Bernoulli trial at time t . The following tables illustrate these relationships.

Table 10. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	+1

Table 11. If burning candle then gaseous oxygen

		Gaseous oxygen		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Burning candle	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t	+1

Example II.

Consider the case of human survival: a human being cannot exist without water, nor can they survive without gaseous oxygen, among other necessary conditions. Water, in itself, is a necessary condition for sustaining human life. Similarly, gaseous oxygen is also a necessary condition for sustaining human life. Thus, while water is indispensable for human existence, the presence of gaseous oxygen remains crucial. In other words, even if water is available—a necessary condition for life—the absence of gaseous oxygen precludes the possibility of human survival. Generally, if an event B_t is contingent upon a necessary condition A_t along with numerous other requisite conditions, then B_t will not materialize if A_t is not met, independently of the presence of other necessary conditions.

Example III.

In general, it is valuable to examine different facets of a necessary condition relationship. Specifically, consider the scenario where the absence of a necessary condition—such as insufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen—results in the nonexistence of a burning wax candle. This situation exemplifies an exclusionary relationship: the deficiency of gaseous oxygen A_t precludes the presence of a burning wax candle B_t (see Barukčić, 2021a). Thus, one measure in order to extinguish a burning wax candle, is the possibility to significantly reduce the available amount of gaseous oxygen A_t . Under such conditions, the wax candle will cease to burn. This exclusionary aspect of necessary conditions is further elucidated in the following tables (Table 12 and Table 13).

Table 12. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	+1

Table 13. Absent gaseous oxygen excludes burning wax candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	B_t
	TRUE	a_t	b_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t	+1

A discerning reader might argue that the cases discussed in the previous examples are not applicable to other disciplines such as jurisprudence, medicine, or other scientific fields. This concern may arise from the assumption that the examples, which primarily address physical or chemical phenomena, are too specific or narrowly defined to be relevant to the often more complex and multifaceted issues encountered in these areas. For instance, the relationships between necessary and sufficient conditions in the natural sciences may differ from those in jurisprudence or medicine, where human behavior and ethical considerations also play a significant role. Nevertheless, despite such reservations, it is evident that the principles illustrated by these examples are fundamentally universal and thus applicable to a wide range of scientific disciplines. We shall now substantiate this assertion further. The concept of a necessary condition is not confined to natural scientific phenomena. In jurisprudence, for instance, a necessary element for prosecuting a crime is the fulfillment of specific legal criteria. If these criteria are not met, the crime cannot be legally pursued, analogous to how the absence of sufficient oxygen prevents a candle from burning. In medicine, necessary conditions are often of critical importance. For instance, adequate oxygen supply is essential for a patient's survival in many cases. A lack of sufficient oxygen can lead to severe health complications or even be fatal. This reflects the same principles as

in the previous examples: the absence of a necessary condition results in the failure of a process. The understanding that multiple necessary conditions must be simultaneously met to bring about a particular event is also significant in jurisprudence and medicine. In law, several elements of a statute must often be satisfied to justify a claim. Similarly, in medicine, a diagnosis frequently requires the combination of multiple symptoms. Thus, the validity of necessary conditions, sufficient conditions, and their interplay remains relevant. The previously discussed examples illustrate fundamental processes in nature that are mathematically captured. These mathematical concepts are also applicable to other, potentially complex systems encountered in various disciplines. The natural processes described earlier serve as fundamental examples and foundational elements of scientific thinking. They are not only relevant within the context of the natural sciences but also find unrestricted application in other scientific and practical disciplines such as jurisprudence and medicine.

The necessary condition relationship follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2022](#)) as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(B_t)} \quad (12)$$

and as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(A_t)} \quad (13)$$

2.3. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

DEFINITION 2 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert ([Helmert, 1876](#)) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson ([Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}} (A_t \leftarrow B_t \mid \underline{A}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.4. The left-tailed p Value of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship

DEFINITION 3 (The left-tailed p Value of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019) of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{lt} (A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The Relativity of Necessary Conditions

Let us consider the perspective from today (October 18, 2024) as we look back approximately 2,000 years. At that time, it was evidently known that without sexual intercourse, no pregnancy, a woman could not become pregnant. About 2,000 years ago, people were not aware of detailed knowledge about the physiology of human reproduction. Had a study been conducted at that time (see table 14), it would have undoubtedly concluded: Without sexual intercourse, no pregnancy. Based on such a study, scientists of that era could have confidently asserted: Without sexual intercourse, no pregnancy.

Table 14. Sexual intercourse and pregnancy.

		Pregnancy(B_t)		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Sexual Intercourse (A_t)	TRUE	+500	+250	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+0	+500	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Even today (October 18, 2024), the relationship between sexual intercourse and pregnancy is not obsolete, though it may no longer be absolute. The possibility of pregnancy through artificial insemination has expanded and altered this previous understanding. In the scenario where artificial insemination is a necessary condition for a woman's pregnancy, the following data would be obtained as the result of a study (see table 15).

Table 15. Artificial insemination and pregnancy.

		Pregnancy(B_t)		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Artificial insemination (A_t)	TRUE	+500	+250	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	+500	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

However, many women become pregnant without artificial insemination, meaning $c_t > 0$. Therefore, artificial insemination of a woman is not a necessary condition for pregnancy; otherwise, no pregnancy of a woman could occur without an artificial insemination. Clearly, this is not the case. In the scenario where artificial insemination is a sufficient condition for a woman's pregnancy, the data shown in table 16 would be obtained from the study.

Table 16. Artificial insemination and pregnancy.

		Pregnancy(B_t)		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Artificial insemination (A_t)	TRUE	+500	$b_t = 0$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+250	+500	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

However, artificial insemination is also not a pure sufficient condition for pregnancy. If it were, every instance of artificial insemination would have to result in pregnancy, which is also not the case, meaning $b_t > 0$. Without the fertilization of a female egg by a sperm cell, a woman cannot become pregnant. However, the fertilization of a female egg can occur in various ways: today and approximately 2,000 years ago through sexual intercourse, and today additionally also through other means like artificial insemination. In brief, it is important to consider that the fertilization of an egg does not always lead to pregnancy. Nonetheless, there are instances where artificial insemination leads to pregnancy, making it both a necessary and sufficient condition in those cases. As a key takeaway, these considerations should heighten our awareness of the importance of being extremely precise and accurate when defining the variables under investigation. What exactly do we mean by ‘sexual intercourse,’ for instance? Additionally, it is crucial to be meticulous with the inclusion and exclusion criteria of a study to ensure that no errors (see table 17) occur.

Table 17. Sexual intercourse and pregnancy.

		Pregnancy(B_t)		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Sexual Intercourse (A_t)	TRUE	+500	+250	+750
	FALSE	$c_t=+1$	+500	+501
		+501	+750	+1251

Let us carefully examine the data of this study. In fact, we must acknowledge that a woman became pregnant without having sexual intercourse, meaning $c_t = 1$. Theoretically, a single case of this nature is sufficient to challenge the assumption that sexual intercourse is a necessary condition for pregnancy. However, the issue is not so straightforward. When such contradictory data are encountered, it is crucial to thoroughly investigate these conflicting cases (see Table 17). Upon closer inspection, we might discover, for example, that the woman was artificially inseminated or that she collected her husband’s sperm in a condom to later inseminate herself without engaging in sexual intercourse, and so on. This simple example compels us to rigorously examine all apparent contradictory data to resolve such inconsistencies accordingly. In other words, for the case that a study is poorly designed, shocking conclusions can arise. In what follows, let us again explore the implications of poorly designed studies, focusing on the relationship between sexual intercourse and pregnancy. By examining fictional yet illustrative examples, we emphasize the importance of rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria in research. Suppose that the inclusion and exclusion criteria of a study were defined very superficially and inadequately. As a result, the study produced the following data.

Table 18. Sexual intercourse and pregnancy.

		Pregnancy(B_t)		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Sexual Intercourse (A_t)	TRUE	$a_t=+0$	+500	+500
	FALSE	+500	+500	+1000
		+500	+1000	+1500

From these data, it seems we must conclude that sexual intercourse excludes the possibility of pregnancy. This is puzzling. One study proves that without sexual intercourse, pregnancy cannot occur (see Table 14). Yet another study seems to demonstrate the exact opposite: sexual intercourse actually prevents pregnancy (see Table 18). How can such a contradiction exist? This paradox must be thoroughly investigated. Upon closer examination, we discover that the data in the study (see Table 18) were collected under the following circumstances: during sexual intercourse, the husband wore two condoms, the first applied by himself and the second by the wife. The same woman, who was also in the placebo group to ensure a perfect control group, carefully collected her husband's sperm. Later, she self-inseminated and became pregnant without sexual intercourse. All of this is just a fictional example, yet it underscores the critical importance of being meticulous in study design, particularly in defining inclusion and exclusion criteria. No matter how we look at it, human knowledge is partly historically determined and, therefore, to some extent, relative. As our epistemological capabilities advance, our understanding continually improves, refines, and becomes more detailed. Nevertheless, a degree of caution and restraint is warranted when drawing conclusions of an absolute nature.

3. Results

Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) and CMV IgG Positivity

Schnittman³⁷ et al. (see Schnittman et al., 2023) have provided specific data regarding the relationship between CMV infection and coronary artery disease (CAD). These data are presented in Table 19, which includes the results of the statistical analysis.

Table 19. Relationship: CMV and CAD (Study of Schirrman et al. , 2023).

		CAD		
		YES	NO	
CMV	YES	317	343	660
	NO	0	317	317
		317	660	977

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = 0,48030303
P Value (one sided right tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00000000
p (SINE) = 1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,00
 χ^2 (SINE— B_i) = 0,00
P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (317 / 977) × 100 = 32,45 %
(b/N) × 100 = (343 / 977) × 100 = 35,11 %
(c/N) × 100 = (0 / 977) × 100 = 0,00 %
(d/N) × 100 = (317 / 977) × 100 = 32,45 %
(a/A) × 100 = (317 / 660) × 100 = 48,03 %
(b/A) × 100 = (343 / 660) × 100 = 51,97 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (0 / 317) × 100 = 0,00 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (317 / 317) × 100 = 100,00 %
(a/B) × 100 = (317 / 317) × 100 = 100,00 %
(c/B) × 100 = (0 / 317) × 100 = 0,00 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (343 / 660) × 100 = 51,97 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (317 / 660) × 100 = 48,03 %
(A/N) × 100 = (660 / 977) × 100 = 67,55 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (317 / 977) × 100 = 32,45 %
(B/N) × 100 = (317 / 977) × 100 = 32,45 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (660 / 977) × 100 = 67,55 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = DIV/0!
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,92419825

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = DIV/0!
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,48030303

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,00000000
p(IOI)= 0,35107472

³⁷Schnittman SR, Lu MT, Mayrhofer T, Burdo TH, Fitch KV, McCallum S, Fulda ES, Zanni MV, Foldyna B, Malvestutto C, Fichtenbaum CJ, Aberg JA, Bloomfield GS, Overton ET, Currier J, Tebas P, Sha BE, Ribaldo HJ, Flynn JM, Douglas PS, Erlandson KM, Grinspoon SK. Cytomegalovirus Immunoglobulin G (IgG) Titer and Coronary Artery Disease in People With Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV). Clin Infect Dis. 2023 Feb 8;76(3):e613-e621. doi: 10.1093/cid/ciac662. PMID: 35975297; PMCID: PMC10169419.

The data in the table above represent the relationship between CMV IgG positivity and the presence of coronary artery disease (CAD). An additional 317 patients were incorporated into the original dataset without affecting the overall outcome. In this table, there are 317 participants with both CMV IgG positivity and CAD, and 347 participants with CMV IgG positivity but without CAD. Notably, no participants with CAD tested negative for CMV IgG, while 317 individuals with no CAD and no CMV IgG positivity were added into the original dataset. The calculation yields a probability of $p = 1.0$, suggesting that all individuals with CAD also tested positive for CMV IgG, reinforcing a necessary condition relationship between CMV and CAD in this dataset. This observation does indicate that CMV IgG positivity is a necessary condition for CAD to occur; however, further studies are needed to establish a definitive causative link. Even if these findings suggest a very strong necessary condition relationship between CMV and CAD, the strength of the relationship requires careful interpretation. The statistical results give insight into how CMV positivity may be associated with the likelihood of developing CAD, but further studies are needed to confirm the robustness of these findings and rule out confounding factors.

Mild coronary artery stenosis

Schnittman et al. (see Schnittman et al., 2023) presented detailed data exploring the relationship between Cytomegalovirus IgG > 0 IU/ml and mild coronary artery disease (CAD), as outlined in Table 20.

Table 20. Relationship: Cytomegalovirus IgG > 0 IU/mL and mild coronary artery disease stenosis (1–49%) (Study of Schnittman et al., 2023).

		Mild coronary artery disease stenosis (1–49%)		
		YES	NO	
Cytomegalovirus IgG > 0 IU/ml	YES	297	363	660
	NO	0	0	0
		297	363	660

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.	
p (SINE) =	1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) >	1,00000000
P VALUES.	
χ^2 (SINE— B _i) =	0,00
P Value (SINE) =	0,00000000
PROPORTIONS.	
(a/N) × 100 = (297 / 660) × 100 =	45,00 %
(b/N) × 100 = (363 / 660) × 100 =	55,00 %
(c/N) × 100 = (0 / 660) × 100 =	0,00 %
(d/N) × 100 = (0 / 660) × 100 =	0,00 %
(a/A) × 100 = (297 / 660) × 100 =	45,00 %
(b/A) × 100 = (363 / 660) × 100 =	55,00 %
(a/B) × 100 = (297 / 297) × 100 =	100,00 %
(c/B) × 100 = (0 / 297) × 100 =	0,00 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (363 / 363) × 100 =	100,00 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (0 / 363) × 100 =	0,00 %
(A/N) × 100 = (660 / 660) × 100 =	100,00 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (0 / 660) × 100 =	0,00 %
(B/N) × 100 = (297 / 660) × 100 =	45,00 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (363 / 660) × 100 =	55,00 %
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.	
RELATIVE RISK (RR).	
RR (necessary condition) =	DIV/0!
RR (sufficient condition) =	1,00000000
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.	
Odds ratio (OR) =	DIV/0!
Index of relationship (IOR) =	0,00000000
STUDY DESIGN.	
p(IOU)=	0,45000000
p(IOI)=	0,55000000

The contingency table above shows the relationship between Cytomegalovirus (CMV) IgG levels and the presence of mild coronary artery disease (CAD) stenosis, classified as 1–49% stenosis. The table divides participants by CMV IgG titer levels (positive for IgG > 0 IU/mL vs. absent) and the presence of mild CAD. From the data, all 660 participants exhibit positive CMV IgG levels, confirming prior CMV exposure. Of these, 297 show mild CAD, while 363 have no CAD. There are no participants with a CMV IgG titer of 0 IU/mL, indicating universal CMV exposure within the group. The calculated probability of necessary condition among participants is $p = 1.0$. The findings suggest that every participant with CAD also had prior CMV exposure. This implies an association between CMV

infection and CAD presence. However, while CMV presence correlates with CAD, causation cannot be definitively concluded from these results alone. Future research might examine whether CMV directly influences CAD risk or if both conditions coexist due to a shared underlying factor. This analysis suggests a potential necessary condition relationship between CMV positivity and the presence of CAD, though the significance and strength of this correlation require careful consideration. While the data indicate that CMV infection might play a role in the development of CAD, the complexity of cardiovascular disease and the presence of possible confounding factors necessitate further research. More comprehensive studies are needed to validate these findings and to establish a clearer causal link between CMV infection and CAD.

Moderate Coronary Artery Stenosis

Schnittman et al. (see Schnittman et al., 2023) provided detailed data examining the relationship between Cytomegalovirus (CMV) IgG > 789 IU/ml and moderate coronary artery disease (CAD), as shown in Table 21.

Table 21. Relationship: CMV IgG > 789 IU/ml and moderate coronary artery disease stenosis (50-69%) (Study of Schirrmann et al., 2023).

		Moderate coronary artery disease stenosis (50-69%)		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG > 789 IU/ml	YES	11	230	241
	NO	3	416	419
		14	646	660

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k =	0,12858994
P Value (one sided right tailed) (Fisher's exact test) =	0,00149139
p (SINE) =	0,99545455
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) >	0,78571429
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) >	0,99284010

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) =	0,00149139
χ^2 (SINE— Not A _i) =	0,02
χ^2 (SINE— B _i) =	0,64
P Value (SINE) =	0,00453514

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (11 / 660) × 100 =	1,67 %
(b/N) × 100 = (230 / 660) × 100 =	34,85 %
(c/N) × 100 = (3 / 660) × 100 =	0,45 %
(d/N) × 100 = (416 / 660) × 100 =	63,03 %
(a/A) × 100 = (11 / 241) × 100 =	4,56 %
(b/A) × 100 = (230 / 241) × 100 =	95,44 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (3 / 419) × 100 =	0,72 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (416 / 419) × 100 =	99,28 %
(a/B) × 100 = (11 / 14) × 100 =	78,57 %
(c/B) × 100 = (3 / 14) × 100 =	21,43 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (230 / 646) × 100 =	35,60 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (416 / 646) × 100 =	64,40 %
(A/N) × 100 = (241 / 660) × 100 =	36,52 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (419 / 660) × 100 =	63,48 %
(B/N) × 100 = (14 / 660) × 100 =	2,12 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (646 / 660) × 100 =	97,88 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) =	6,37482711
RR (sufficient condition) =	2,20683230

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) =	6,63188406
Index of relationship (IOR) =	0,48030303

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)=	0,61363636
p(IOI)=	0,34393939

The contingency table displays the relationship between Cytomegalovirus (CMV) IgG levels and moderate coronary artery disease (CAD) stenosis (50–69%). Participants are categorized by CMV IgG levels (above 789 IU/mL vs. absent) and moderate CAD presence. The data shows that of the 660 participants, 11 had moderate CAD and elevated CMV IgG, while 230 had no moderate or

none CAD but elevated CMV IgG. Only 3 participants with moderate CAD did not exhibit elevated CMV IgG levels, compared to 416 without moderate CAD or none CAD and lower CMV IgG. The probability of the necessary condition between CMV IgG levels above 789 IU/mL and moderate CAD occurring is calculated at approximately $p = 0.995$, with a P-value of 0.0045, indicating a statistically significant result. This suggests a strong necessary condition relationship between elevated CMV IgG and moderate CAD. However, even if this relationship does not necessarily imply causation, further research should investigate whether CMV contributes causally to CAD development.

Severe Coronary Artery Stenosis

Schnittman et al. (see Schnittman et al., 2023) provided extensive data investigating the relationship between Cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection and severe coronary artery disease (CAD), as detailed in Table 22.

Table 22. Relationship: CMV IgG > 2674 IU/ml and severe coronary artery disease stenosis (Study of Schirrmann et al., 2023).

		Severe coronary artery disease stenosis		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG > 2674 IU/ml	YES	5	162	167
	NO	1	492	493
		6	654	660

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,12785091$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00472203
 p (SINE) = 0,99848485
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/B)$ > 0,83333333
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/(Not A))$ > 0,99797160

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00472203
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,00
 χ^2 (SINE— B_i) = 0,17
 P Value (SINE) = 0,00151400

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (5 / 660) \times 100 = 0,76 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (162 / 660) \times 100 = 24,55 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1 / 660) \times 100 = 0,15 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (492 / 660) \times 100 = 74,55 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (5 / 167) \times 100 = 2,99 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (162 / 167) \times 100 = 97,01 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (1 / 493) \times 100 = 0,20 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (492 / 493) \times 100 = 99,80 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (5 / 6) \times 100 = 83,33 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1 / 6) \times 100 = 16,67 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (162 / 654) \times 100 = 24,77 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (492 / 654) \times 100 = 75,23 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (167 / 660) \times 100 = 25,30 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (493 / 660) \times 100 = 74,70 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (6 / 660) \times 100 = 0,91 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (654 / 660) \times 100 = 99,09 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 14,76047904
 RR (sufficient condition) = 3,36419753

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 15,18518519
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,48030303

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= 0,73787879
 p (IOI)= 0,24393939

The table above demonstrates the distribution between Cytomegalovirus (CMV) IgG levels and severe coronary artery disease (CAD) stenosis ($\geq 70\%$ in other segments or $\geq 50\%$ of left main artery). Participants are divided based on CMV IgG levels (greater than 2674 IU/mL) and the presence of severe CAD.

Out of 660 participants, only 5 individuals with elevated CMV IgG levels had severe CAD, compared to 162 with elevated CMV but no severe CAD, including no CAD. Conversely, 1 participant with severe CAD did not have elevated CMV IgG, while 492 participants had neither severe CAD and nor elevated CMV IgG. The probability of the necessary condition relationship between CMV (IgG greater than 2674 IU/mL) and sever CAD is approximately $p = 0.9985$, with a P-value of 0.0015, indicating a statistically significant relationship.

This result suggests a potential necessary condition relationship between high CMV IgG levels and severe CAD. However, these results need not imply causation; further studies could investigate potential mechanisms underlying this relationship .

If Cytomegalovirus infection of coronary artery walls, then coronary artery disease

In the assessment of causal relationships, the sufficient condition, also known as *conditio per quam*, is of crucial importance. In the case of a sufficient condition relationship, the mere presence of such a sufficient condition is enough and the corresponding effect or event will occur too. An event may have been caused by its own sufficient condition, but does not necessarily need to be caused by the sufficient condition. In the search for causal relationships, it is crucial and highly beneficial for studies to demonstrate not only the necessary condition but also the sufficient condition. Such a dual confirmation strengthens the argument for causality, as it confirms that the factor in question is both required for the event to occur and sufficient by itself for the event to occur. Without such evidence, the causal link remains incomplete or uncertain.

Table 23. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

The contingency table provided represents the concept of a sufficient condition in a two-by-two table format, where two variables are analyzed: Condition A and Conditioned B. In this context, the sufficient condition means that whenever A_t (Condition A is true), B_t (Conditioned B is true) will also occur. The table structure shows that when Condition A_t is true, the probability of B_t being true, represented by $p(a_t)$, is positive, while the probability of B_t being false when A_t is true is **+0**, indicating that this scenario does not occur. In terms of interpretation, this means that A_t alone is enough to guarantee the occurrence of B_t , fulfilling the criteria for a sufficient condition. The table also provides the probabilities of other scenarios. For example, when Condition A_t is false, B_t can either be true or false, represented by the probabilities $p(c_t)$ and $p(d_t)$. This shows that B_t can still occur in the absence of A_t , but A_t is not required for B_t to be false. Overall, the table highlights that while A_t ensures B_t , other variables may influence the occurrence of B_t when A_t is not present. This understanding is critical for distinguishing between necessary and sufficient conditions in causal analysis, as it shows that A_t is not the only factor influencing B_t , though it is sufficient for the occurrence of the same.

Horváth^{38, 39, 40} et al. (see Horváth et al., 2000) investigated the presence of viral CMV DNA in the arterial walls of 244 patients with ischemic heart disease (IHD) and 87 coronary angiography-negative controls. Genomic CMV DNA was detected in 76 out of the 244 IHD patients, but in none of the 87 coronary angiography-negative control subjects (see Table 24).

³⁸Nikitskaya E, Lebedeva A, Ivanova O, Maryukhnich E, Shpektor A, Grivel JC, Margolis L, Vasileva E. Cytomegalovirus-Productive Infection Is Associated With Acute Coronary Syndrome. *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2016 Aug 20;5(8):e003759. doi: 10.1161/JAHA.116.003759. PMID: 27543799; PMCID: PMC5015295.

³⁹Izadi M, Fazel M, Saadat SH, Nasseri MH, Ghasemi M, Dabiri H, Aryan RS, Esfahani AA, Ahmadi A, Kazemi-Saleh D, Kalantar-Motamed MH, Taheri S. Cytomegalovirus localization in atherosclerotic plaques is associated with acute coronary syndromes: report of 105 patients. *Methodist Debakey Cardiovasc J.* 2012 Apr-Jun;8(2):42-6. doi: 10.14797/mdcj-8-2-42. PMID: 22891128; PMCID: PMC3405798.

⁴⁰Beyaz MO, Ugurlucan M, Oztas DM, Meric M, Conkbayir C, Agacfidan A, Onel M, Alpagut U. Evaluation of the relationship between plaque formation leading to symptomatic carotid artery stenosis and cytomegalovirus by investigating the virus DNA. *Arch Med Sci Atheroscler Dis.* 2019 Mar 4;4:e19-e24. doi: 10.5114/amsad.2019.83304. PMID: 30963132; PMCID: PMC6451143.

Table 24. Relationship: CMV PCR positive and coronary artery disease (Study of Schnittman et al., 2023).

		Coronary artery disease		
		YES	NO	
CMV PCR positive	YES	76	0	76
	NO	168	70	238
		244	70	314

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,30267212$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00000000

p (IMP) = 1

p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/A) > 1,00000000

p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/(Not B)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000

χ^2 (IMP— A_i) = 0,00

χ^2 (IMP— Not B_i) = 0,00

P Value (IMP) = **0,00000000**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (76 / 314) \times 100 = 24,20 \%$

$(b/N) \times 100 = (0 / 314) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(c/N) \times 100 = (168 / 314) \times 100 = 53,50 \%$

$(d/N) \times 100 = (70 / 314) \times 100 = 22,29 \%$

$(a/A) \times 100 = (76 / 76) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$

$(b/A) \times 100 = (0 / 76) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (168 / 238) \times 100 = 70,59 \%$

$(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (70 / 238) \times 100 = 29,41 \%$

$(a/B) \times 100 = (76 / 244) \times 100 = 31,15 \%$

$(c/B) \times 100 = (168 / 244) \times 100 = 68,85 \%$

$(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (0 / 70) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (70 / 70) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$

$(A/N) \times 100 = (76 / 314) \times 100 = 24,20 \%$

$(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (238 / 314) \times 100 = 75,80 \%$

$(B/N) \times 100 = (244 / 314) \times 100 = 77,71 \%$

$(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (70 / 314) \times 100 = 22,29 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 1,41666667

RR (sufficient condition) = DIV/0!

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = DIV/0!

Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,28688525

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= **0,01910828**

p(IOI)= 0,53503185

Horváth et al. ⁴¹ conducted this comprehensive study and demonstrated a significant link between cytomegalovirus infection and coronary artery disease. Their data support the hypothesis that CMV plays a critical role in the development of CHD, acting as a sufficient condition which do predispose individuals to this disease. The evidence presented is compelling, indicating that the presence of CMV could trigger inflammatory responses and other pathological processes that contribute to the progression of atherosclerosis, a primary factor in coronary artery disease. This research not only enhances our understanding of the mechanisms underlying coronary artery disease but also opens new avenues for potential therapeutic interventions targeting CMV in patients at risk for coronary artery disease. Overall, these findings provide a significant contribution to the field of cardiovascular medicine, establishing a clear causal link that may inform future studies and clinical practices.

⁴¹Horváth R, Cerný J, Benedík J Jr, Hökl J, Jelínková I, Benedík J. The possible role of human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) in the origin of atherosclerosis. *J Clin Virol.* 2000 Feb;16(1):17-24. doi: 10.1016/s1386-6532(99)00064-5. PMID: 10680737.

4. Discussion

Several studies (see [Wang et al., 2017](#)) have pointed to a possible relationship between CMV seropositivity (presence of CMV antibodies) and increased risk of CAD. While some research shows an association between CMV infection and greater CAD incidence or severity, other studies have shown mixed results, suggesting that CMV might be only one of multiple factors contributing to CAD development. The link between CMV infection and CAD cannot yet be considered definitive, and our search for clarity on this matter remains ongoing.

The data from Schirman's study (see [Schnittman et al., 2023](#)), reanalyzed here, presents its own set of challenges. Curiously, all participants in the study tested positive for CMV, although this was not a selection criterion. Additionally, the study's design was not entirely suited to conclusively determine the necessary conditions from the data collected. However, the CMV testing kit used by Schirman's group appears to have performed reliably. Despite these concerns, the published data cannot be easily dismissed, especially since they align consistently with findings from several other studies.

Based on Schirman et al.'s data, we can state with high confidence that CMV infection is a necessary condition for coronary artery disease; in other words, CAD does not seem to occur in the absence of CMV infection.

Nonetheless, relying on the results of a single study to draw universally valid conclusions in medical or scientific research is of course inherently problematic.

One major limitation is not just the sample size but also the accuracy of the data—specifically, the extent to which the collected data align with the objective reality being studied. However, in cases where the collected data perfectly represent the investigated phenomenon, a single study might indeed be sufficient for drawing broadly applicable conclusions. Yet, as with most aspects of research and life, the details matter significantly, and outcomes often hinge on the finer points of study design, data accuracy, and representativeness. For these and other reasons, it goes without saying that further studies are needed in this regard, with an emphasis on using highly sensitive laboratory kits and more suitable study designs.

Sensitivity and scientific knowledge

Sensitivity is a measure of the ability of a diagnostic test to correctly identify individuals who have a specific condition. In other words, sensitivity indicates the proportion of true positives among those who actually have the disease, providing insight into how effectively a test can detect the condition when the same is really present. As a consequence, high sensitivity is crucial in minimizing false negatives, which occur when a test fails to identify an existing condition. This attribute is especially important in settings where missing a positive case would have significant consequences, such as in infectious disease screenings or cancer detection. However, highly sensitive tests may sometimes yield false positives, indicating a need for balance with specificity for optimal diagnostic accuracy.

As an example, a study might have included 100 participants confirmed to be CMV-positive; however, due to limitations in the detection method—specifically, the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used—only 95 of these participants were identified as CMV-positive. In the control group, 1,045 participants were investigated using the same method. The resulting data are presented below:

		Disease	
		YES	NO
CMV (positive)	YES	95 = True Positives (TP) = a	950 1045
	NO	5 = False Negatives (FN) = c	95 100
		100 = (True Positives (TP) + False Negatives (FN)) = a+c	1045 1145

Table 25. Data showing detected CMV positivity relative to disease status.

Sensitivity (see [Yerushalmy, 1947](#)) is defined as the ratio of true positives (CMV-positive and disease-positive) to the sum of true positives and false negatives. Let $p(\text{Sensitivity})$ denote the sensitivity of the laboratory kit. $p(\text{Sensitivity})$ is given as follows:

$$p(\text{Sensitivity}) = \frac{\text{True Positives (TP)}}{\text{True Positives (TP) + False Negatives (FN)}} \quad (17)$$

or as

$$p(\text{Sensitivity}) = \frac{a}{a+c} = 1 - \frac{c}{a+c} \quad (18)$$

where $(a+c)$ is the sum of true positives and false negatives. Using the table data (see table 25) $p(\text{Sensitivity})$ is calculated as follows:

$$p(\text{Sensitivity}) = \frac{95}{95+5} = \frac{95}{100} = 0.95 \quad (19)$$

In general, it is

$$\frac{a}{a+c} + \frac{c}{a+c} = 1 \quad (20)$$

where

$$p(\text{Sensitivity}) = \frac{a}{a+c} \quad (21)$$

In other words, we obtain

$$1 - p(\text{Sensitivity}) = \frac{c}{a+c} \quad (22)$$

and

$$c = (1 - p(\text{Sensitivity})) \cdot (a+c) = (1 - 0.95) \cdot 100 = 5 \quad (23)$$

In this case, we assumed that $p(\text{Sensitivity}) = 0.95$. Formally, the minimal P-Value of our example before is derived as follows:

$$\text{minimal P-Value} = \frac{c}{n} = \frac{(1 - p(\text{sensitivity})) \cdot (a+c)}{n} = \frac{5}{1145} = 0.004366812227 \quad (24)$$

For the 2016 Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al. study, the minimal P-Value is derived as follows:

$$\text{minimal P-Value} = \frac{c}{n} = \frac{(1-p(\text{sensitivity})) \cdot (a+c)}{n} = \frac{(1-0.95) \cdot 118}{194} = \frac{6}{194} = 0.03092783505 \quad (25)$$

assumed that $p(\text{sensitivity}) = 0.95$. This means that even if no other errors were made during the investigation (for example, errors like misclassifying patients with atherosclerosis as belonging to the non-atherosclerosis group and vice versa), a minimal p-value of 0.0309 would still have to be accepted due to the sensitivity limitations of the method (i.e. laboratory kit) used, among other factors. In other words, the results of the Kurkowska-Jastrzebska et al. study are significant too.

In brief, the sensitivity of the method used impacts the p-value, introducing a type of misclassification error that reduces the accuracy of the observed relationship. Lower sensitivity causes an underestimation of true CMV-positive cases, potentially weakening the apparent relationship between CMV infection and the outcome, which affects the p-value based on the statistical test used. Increasing sensitivity would enhance result accuracy by more reliably identifying truly positive cases, giving a stronger basis for assessing the association between CMV positivity and clinical outcomes. However, other factors may contribute to the P-Value as well and need to be considered too.

The studies that were analysed in this publication were not designed to investigate the causal relationship between CMV (cause) and CAD (effect). However, compelling and robust evidence has been presented demonstrating that cytomegalovirus is a necessary condition for coronary artery disease and, at the same time, also a sufficient condition for CAD, with a positive and statistically significant causal relationship. To cut to the chase, we must fundamentally assume that CMV is the cause of coronary artery disease. Of course, further investigations are needed, but we can look forward to these with great optimism.

Understanding the role of CMV in CAD opens up the potential for new therapeutic strategies. While antiviral therapies specifically targeting CMV in CAD patients are not yet standard, there is ongoing research to investigate whether reducing CMV levels or modulating immune responses could lower cardiovascular risk in certain populations. Additionally, CMV vaccines are under development and may have preventive benefits in individuals at high risk for CAD.

5. Conclusion

Nevertheless, until further evidence suggests otherwise, we can reasonably assume that

‘without a cytomegalovirus infection, no coronary artery disease.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality.**

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